

MULTI-SCALE MODELING OF THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF SHORT GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYAMIDE NOTCHED SPECIMENS

E. Belmonte^{1,2*}, M. De Monte², M. Quaresimin³

¹Department of Management and Engineering, University of Padova
Stradella S. Nicola 3, 36100 Vicenza (Italy)

Email: Enrico.Belmonte@de.bosch.com, web page: <http://www.gest.unipd.it/en>

²Robert Bosch GmbH, Corporate Sector Research and Advance Engineering – Advance Production
Technology 1 – Plastics Engineering, Renningen (Germany)

Email: Matthias.DeMonte@de.bosch.com, web page: <http://www.bosch.com>

³Department of Management and Engineering, University of Padova
Stradella S. Nicola 3, 36100 Vicenza (Italy)

Email: marino.quaresimin@unipd.it, web page: <http://www.gest.unipd.it/en>

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a multi-scale strategy for the lifetime prediction, in terms of crack initiation, of short fiber reinforced polyamide specimens. Fatigue tests of specimens characterized by a central molded-in slit were carried out. In the first part, the development of a two-dimensional geometric representation of the real microstructure around the notch is presented. The second part of the paper deals with the formulation of the criterion for the durability assessment. A local threshold stress which includes the microscopic matrix stress concentrations is used to summarize the fatigue data for different fiber volume fractions within a single scatter band. The strengths and the weaknesses of the proposed criterion as well as its possible extensions are also discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of Short Fiber Reinforced Plastics (SFRPs) in the automotive sector is motivated by several reasons, among which: 1) Minimization of the vehicle weight; 2) Reduction of the manufacturing costs; 3) Design freedom. SFRPs exhibit high strength to weight ratio, high chemical and temperature resistance. Such characteristics make these materials ideal candidates for metal replacement in under-the-hood applications. Under-the-hood components are exposed to cyclic loading due to vibrations, pulsating pressure, temperature variations. Approaches to durability become essential to predict the lifetime already in the design phase.

In the literature, some phenomenological approaches for the lifetime prediction of SFRPs are available. Most of them are extensions of models originally developed for homogeneous, isotropic materials. Such approaches require test data to determine the phenomenological constants and do not provide the physical insight needed to improve the material performance. The Tsai-Hill criterion was extended by De Monte et al. [1], [2] to predict the influence of the fiber orientation on the tensile and fatigue strength of PA66-GF35 plain specimens. The volume-based Strain Energy Density (SED) approach originally developed by Lazzarin et al. [3], [4], [5] for metals, was extended by De Monte

and coworkers [6] in order to predict the lifetime of PA66-GF35 specimens weakened by different notch geometries. The SED model was further extended by Schaaf and coworkers [7] for the lifetime prediction of a PBT-GF30 under thermomechanical loading. Recently, thanks to the increase of the computational power and the improvements of the experimental methods for the damage investigation, models able to take into account the microstructure have been proposed [8].

In this paper, a multi-scale model for the lifetime prediction up to crack initiation of SFRPs is presented. In certain components, the initiation of a crack corresponds to the component failure. An example is the fuel rail shown by Sonsino and Moosbrugger in [9]. In that case, the occurrence of a crack may lead to fuel leakage compromising the functioning of the component. According to Talreja [10], the first step of a durability approach is the stress analysis of the considered geometry under expected service environment using the assumed material model. SFRPs are heterogeneous materials. In addition to the macro stress concentrations at geometric discontinuities, microscopic stress concentrations emerge due to the mismatch between the elastic properties of fibers and matrix. The knowledge of the fiber distribution at crack initiation is thus of great interest since it enables the study of typical matrix micro-stress concentrations. Analyzing the microstructure around a molded-in notch in a longitudinal injected specimen, the authors revealed the occurrence of through-the-thickness oriented fibers [11]. Building on these achievements, in the section 3 a geometric description of the microstructure around the notch is illustrated. In the section 4, a multi-scale modeling strategy is proposed. In order to study the effect of the fiber distribution on the fatigue material behavior, polyamides characterized by different fiber fractions were considered.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

In this work, unreinforced and short glass fiber reinforced polyamides (PA66) were used. The material designations (PA66, PA66-GF15, PA66-GF25, PA66-GF35, PA66-GF50) correspond to 0%, 15%, 25%, 35%, 50% weight fiber fraction respectively. Dog-bone plain specimens were tested under quasi-static loading to measure elastic and strength properties of the considered material systems. Notched specimens were tested under fatigue loading. The specimen geometries are shown in Figure 1. Both plain and notched specimens were longitudinally injected. The notch is obtained with an insert within the mold. This choice stems from the fact that real-world components generally do not need any post-molding milling operations. All the geometric discontinuities are already within the mold.

Figure 1: Specimen geometry and dimensions (in mm); plain specimen on the left; notched specimen on the right (see the enlargement of the notch tip at the bottom right of the figure).

Static and fatigue tests were carried out at room temperature without controlling the humidity level. Just after molding, the specimens were stored in drums containing a drying agent. Hence, we assume that all the specimens were tested in Dry-As-Molded (DAM) conditions. A Zwick/Roell Z050 was used to test plain specimens under quasi-static loading. The crosshead rate was kept slow for the measurement of the Young's modulus (1mm/min) and accelerated (5mm/min) in the second part of the test until specimen failure. The tensile properties for different fiber volume fractions are summarized

in Table 1. Interestingly, while the Young's modulus (E) and the Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) increase with increasing fiber fraction, the strain to failure (ε at failure) of the reinforced materials is independent of the fiber content. Similar results were reported also by Bernasconi and Cosmi [12]. Uniaxial fatigue tests were carried out on a servo-hydraulic testing machine, equipped with a load cell of 25 kN. Fatigue tests were performed under load control in tension-tension mode (load ratio $R=0$). The testing frequency was kept low in order to avoid the material self heating. In Figure 2b the fatigue results are reported by plotting the nominal net stress amplitude against the number of cycles to crack initiation (dotted line) and to failure (solid line). Eq. (1) was used to fit the fatigue data.

$$N = 10^6 \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_A(10^6)}{\sigma_a(N)} \right)^k \quad (1)$$

$\sigma_A(1E6)$ is the stress amplitude at $N=1E6$ cycles, k is the inverse slope of the S-N line. For the crack initiation detection, an optical capturing method was used [13]. The fitting parameters used in the eq. (1) are reported in Table 1.

Figure 2: (a) Static tests of plain specimens for different fiber volume fractions; (b) Fatigue tests of notched specimens for different fiber volume fractions.

Material	E [MPa]	UTS [MPa]	ε at failure [%]
PA66-GF15	6176	120	2.50
PA66-GF25	8991	164	2.70
PA66-GF35	10899	184	2.60
PA66-GF50	16025	202	2.20

Table 1: Tensile properties of short glass fiber reinforced polyamides (PA66) having different fiber volume fractions.

Material	Initiation		Failure	
	$\sigma_A(N=1E6)$	k	$\sigma_A(N=1E6)$	k
PA66-GF15	10.31	9.72	10.80	9.17
PA66-GF25	12.42	7.46	13.99	7.59
PA66-GF35	15.10	7.60	16.94	6.81
PA66-GF50	15.03	6.18	18.99	6.95

Table 2: S-N lines up to crack initiation and up to failure of short glass fiber reinforced polyamides (PA66) having different fiber volume fractions.

3 EQUIVALENT DESCRIPTION OF THE MICROSTRUCTURE

In this section, a statistical equivalency approach for the description of the fiber distribution at crack initiation is proposed. According to Pyrz [14], SFRPs can be described as statistically homogeneous materials. This means that the effective material properties can be obtained by averaging over a Representative Volume Element (RVE). Averaging is useful if the global elastic material properties have to be calculated. Instead, damage initiation is governed by local effects. The mismatch between the elastic properties of fibers and matrix and the interaction between neighboring fibers lead to matrix stress concentrations which are preferred locations for crack initiation. Segurado and Llorca [15] studied the effect of particles spatial distributions in a RVE on the local stress distributions and the elastic global properties. They observed that the spatial arrangement of the particles (in particular the clusters of particles) influences the matrix stress peaks whereas it does not affect the effective material properties of the composite material. Bulsara and coworkers [16] investigated the RVE size with respect to the damage mechanisms matrix cracking and fiber-matrix debonding.

Figure 3 shows the statistical distribution of the maximum principal stress on the matrix in a real material volume around a molded-in notch tip. On the right of Figure 3, three contour plots represent the same distribution of the maximum principal stress but varying the lowest limit of the contour scale. For example, on the contour plot at the top-right of Figure 3 the stresses starting from 2 MPa are plotted. The microscopic matrix stress concentrations occur either between through-the-thickness oriented fibers or at the ends of longitudinally oriented fibers and correspond to a small fraction of the total stresses. Through-the-thickness oriented fibers are restricted to a thin layer surrounding the notch, where damage is most likely to initiate.

Figure 3: Max principal stress contours plots referring to percentage portions of the area under the stress distribution curve.

The microstructure shown in Figure 3 closely reproduces the fiber orientation distribution in the reality. However, the effort required for preparing and scanning the sample and for the analysis of the X-Ray Computed Tomography (CT) datasets discourages the extension of this procedure for large experimental campaigns. The proposed strategy for the development of an equivalent geometric

representation of the fiber orientation distribution aims to reproduce the typical observed matrix stress concentrations.

In a first approximation, the failure process in specimens weakened by molded-in notches can be divided into two parts. In a first phase, matrix cracking occurs in a zone characterized by clusters of through-the-thickness oriented fibers. From this point on, the crack propagates in a fiber avoidance mode leading to a zig-zag pattern mostly avoiding in-plane oriented fibers. Focusing on the damage initiation only, the microstructure was represented as a 2D layer surrounding the notch and containing a random distribution of through-the-thickness oriented fibers (Figure 4). The nominal fiber fraction was kept constant. The fiber diameter (d_f) was kept constant and equal to $10\mu\text{m}$. A hard-core method was used by applying a uniform distribution for the fiber centers and considering a minimum permitted distance ($\text{dist}=1.05*d_f$) between any two centers. The size of the geometric representation of the microstructure is related to the layer within which through-the-thickness oriented fibers were observed. The layer width is set to 3.5 times the fiber diameter and indicates the distance delimiting damage initiation area. The fiber-matrix interface was not modeled. Perfect fiber-matrix bonding was assumed. Plane strain elements were used in the simulation thus assuming that the fibers are endless. The element size was kept constant for various fiber fractions. The simplifications introduced in the geometric representation imply that the stress concentrations are only affected by the distance between neighboring fibers. Effects such the fibers overlapping as well as the influence of the fiber orientation were not taken into account.

The boundary conditions of the microstructure were assigned using the submodeling technique. Two-dimensional homogeneous, isotropic, linear elastic simulations of the entire specimen were performed by only varying the Young's modulus depending on the fiber volume fraction (Figure 4a). The adopted values of the Young's modulus are summarized in Table 1. The nodes on the bottom face of the specimen were constrained in all the degrees of freedom while uniform pressure, equal to 1 MPa was applied to the top surface. Because of the huge size difference between the global model and the microstructure, an additional sub-model having the properties of the global model was simulated (Figure 4b). The displacement field resulting from the analysis of the first sub model model was finally assigned to the second sub-model (Figure 4c). In the second sub-model, fibers and matrix were explicitly modeled. In this case, the linear elastic material properties of fibers and matrix were adopted from [1].

Figure 4: Description of the submodeling technique: (a) global model; (b) first sub model; (c) second sub model. One homogeneous material model was assigned to the global and the first sub model while two different material models (fibers and matrix) were assigned to the second sub model.

4 FORMULATION OF THE FAILURE CRITERION AND ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

Figure 5 shows the contours of the maximum principal stress in the matrix for different fiber fractions. For a given percentage area under the statistical stress distribution curve (Figure 3), the corresponding threshold stress is higher for lower fiber fractions. The reason is that the Young's modulus assigned to the global model influences the displacement distribution. A lower Young's modulus results in higher displacements transferred to the submodel. On the other hand, the interfiber distance decreases with increasing fiber volume fraction resulting in higher local stresses. The Young's modulus of the global model and the interfiber distance are the two factors which influence the matrix stress distribution in the microstructure.

Figure 5: Contours of the microscopic matrix stress distributions varying the fiber volume fraction.

We followed a statistical approach for the derivation of a local, critical stress-based variable to be used in the multi-scale model. Taking as example the PA66-GF35 material, 20 random microstructures were generated. For each microstructure, the highest maximum principal stress and the stress

thresholds referring to different portions of the total area under the stress distribution were calculated. For each stress threshold, the average value over the 20 microstructures and the standard deviation are reported in Figure 6. For a correct analysis of the scatter, the standard deviation was divided by the average value of the corresponding stress threshold. The high scatter shown by the highest maximum principal stress prevents its use as failure variable in the multi-scale model. Instead, the threshold stress value referring to a specific portion of the total area under the curve exhibits a lower scatter. The standard deviation diminishes with increasing of the area under the stress distribution curve. However, if we take into account a large portion of the total area, we include stress regions which do not participate to the damage phenomenon (Figure 3). Following an engineering approach, the adopted stress threshold is the result of a trade-off between these two objectives. Finally, we found that the stress threshold referring to the 10% of the area under the stress distribution curve exhibits a low scatter and identifies the stress concentrations which correspond to the potential sources of irreversibility in the microstructures (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Evaluation of the average value and standard deviation of the local matrix threshold stress related to different percentage areas under the curve over 20 random microstructures.

The fatigue data were rearranged in terms of local matrix threshold stress amplitude σ_A^* according to the eq.2.

$$\sigma_A^* = \sigma_A \cdot \sigma_I^* \quad (2)$$

Where σ_A is the nominal fatigue strength for a given number of cycles and σ_I^* is the concentration factor expressed as the threshold stress related to the 10% of the area under the matrix stress distribution curve when a pressure equal to 1[MPa] is applied to the global model. The data represented in terms of local matrix threshold stress amplitude fall within a single band as shown in Figure 7. The scatter index T_σ is the ratio between the stress values at 90% and 10% failure probability.

Figure 7: Fatigue data plotted in terms of nominal stress amplitude (a) and local matrix threshold stress amplitude against the number of cycles to crack initiation.

Assuming that σ_a^* is constant for each fiber volume fraction, the model enables the calculation of the nominal S-N curves for different fiber volume fractions basing on a single calibration curve. In fact the parameter σ_1^* can be calculated through a linear elastic FE analysis.

Figure 8 shows the performance of the model reporting the experimental number of cycles against the estimated values using as calibration curve the S-N line referring to one of the considered fiber volume fractions. The dashed lines indicate the $\pm 200\%$ error bands. Given a set of fatigue data for a specific fiber volume fraction, the relation between the stress amplitude (σ_a) and the number of cycles to crack initiation (N) is expressed by the eq. 1. The same equation is valid for the S-N line plotted in terms of local matrix threshold stress amplitude (σ_a^*) against number of cycles to crack initiation (N) (eq. 3).

$$\left(\sigma_a^*\right)^k \cdot N = \text{const} \quad (3)$$

The slope of the S-N line (k) is kept constant. Given a value of the stress amplitude, it is possible to calculate the number of cycles to crack initiation for any other fiber volume fraction. For example, in the eq. 4, the calibration curve is the S-N line for PA66-GF35.

$$N_a = N_A \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_A^*}{\sigma_a^*}\right)^k = N_A \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_A^{GF35} \cdot \sigma_I^{*GF35}}{\sigma_A^? \cdot \sigma_I^{*?}}\right)^k \quad (4)$$

Where $N_A=1E6$ cycles, σ_A^{GF35} is the stress amplitude referring to 1E6 cycles, σ_I^{*GF35} the threshold stress limiting the 10% of the area under the stress distribution curve when a pressure equal to 1 [MPa] is applied to the global model. The appendix “?” indicates the fiber volume fraction of the outputted S-N line.

Figure 8 Performance of the criterion in terms of fatigue life considering as calibration curve the S-N curve of PA66-GF15 (a); PA66-GF25 (b); PA66-GF35 (c); PA66-GF50 (d); the dashed lines indicate the $\pm 200\%$ error bands.

Despite the simplifications included in the model, the proposed multi-scale strategy gives acceptable results and in particular appears to be a rapid tool for the derivation of S-N lines for different fiber configurations.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A multi-scale modeling strategy for the prediction of the lifetime up to crack initiation in notched specimens was presented. Despite its simplicity, the proposed multi-scale model gives good results requiring only one calibration curve. The approximations of the model (isotropic material model for the global model, bi-dimensional model, perfectly aligned fibers, absence of an interface model) could be removed without varying the proposed multi-scale strategy. The microstructure modeled in this work is representative of specimen weakened by a molded-in central notch. The fiber distribution should be investigated also for other specimen geometries and typical regions for crack initiation in real-world-components. In a future work, the fatigue data of plain specimens will be reanalyzed using the same multi-scale model.

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